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THE REPUBLICS OF POLAND AND AZERBAIJAN IN THE MODERN INTERNATIONAL ARENA (1990-2010)

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Abstract

The Azerbaijani and Polish Republics that got rid the Soviet influence, like many countries that regained their independence, began to look for new foreign policy priorities and development paths, and demonstrate their position in solving global issues. One of the most important priorities of Polish policy has become "The New Eastern Europe". In particular, in relations with the countries of Ukraine, Moldova, the Western Balkans, and the South Caucasus, Poland sought to stimulate democratic development in these countries by strengthening partnerships. The period of L.Kaczynski's presidency can be seen as Poland's offensive policy in international affairs. At this time, "Eastern politics" Poland declared its main task to preserve the independence of Ukraine and Belarus, which was designed for the prospects of these countries joining NATO and the EU.

Its presence in a number of pan-European and regional organizations, such as the OSCE, the OIC, the CIS, and Guam, played an important role in establishing beneficial relations between the newly independent Azerbaijan and various countries. Since 1992, Azerbaijan has also begun close contacts with the Black Sea Economic Cooperation Organization (BSEC), which includes states such as Bulgaria, Russia, Turkey, and Albania and which fights environmental crimes, terrorism, corruption, kidnapping.

Azerbaijan's activities in the Organization of Islamic Cooperation are of particular importance. It was thanks to the OIC that Armenia was officially recognized as an aggressor country by international organizations. The Republic of Azerbaijan, adhering to the principles of joint struggle for security in the Euro-Atlantic area, participated in peacekeeping operations led by NATO.

Keywords: international relations, international organizations, post-Soviet period, foreign policy of Azerbaijani, Polish relations

In recent years, the Eurasian space, which covers many countries of the former USSR, has become the arena of various political and economic processes. Along with various complex processes, the serious transformations taking place in these countries affect international politics and security. Integration and disintegration processes are observed against the background of a clash of strategic interests of influential regional and non-regional players. The collapse of the Soviet Empire also put an end to the existence of military, political and economic institutions associated with the socialist system. The Azerbaijani and Polish Republics, which got rid Soviet influence, like many countries that regained their independence, began to look for new foreign policy priorities and development paths, and demonstrate their position in solving global issues.

The place of independent Poland in the international system and important aspects of its foreign policy have been the focus of attention of a number of Polish and foreign researchers, such as A.Smolar, R.Kuzniar, V.Volobuyev, M.Chesnovsky, S.Sulovsky, M. Rush. The monograph of the Adviser to the President of Poland on International Affairs, Professor R. Kuzniar "Poland's Foreign Policy after 1989", published in 2006 [5] has become one of the necessary scientific works on the study of foreign policy issues in modern Poland. This scholarly work, popular among international relations and diplomacy specialists at Polish universities and beyond, explores

Poland's role in the international arena after 1989. The book is particularly notable for its analysis of Poland's accession to NATO and the European Union. The year 2004, when Poland joined the European Union and entered into new political realities, is considered the year of a turning point in the foreign policy of this country. F. Kushnarev and S.Zaitz In an article published by in 2022, Poland's activities in the European Union are analyzed. The authors gave a brief overview of the events taking place in Ukraine at the present stage and the reaction of the Polish authorities in the EU. It is noted here that Poland is at the forefront of the "anti-Russian" policy, and the country is trying to increase its credibility in the EU and in the international arena in this way [18]. M.Chesnovsky's book "the countries of Central Europe" [25] analyzes the problems of systemic transformation in the countries of Central Europe, examines their place and role in the system of international relations, taking into account their domestic political characteristics.

Azerbaijan's place in the international arena and the foreign policy pursued during these years have been the object of scientific research by a number of researchers. Issues of ensuring the national interests of the Republic take place in the research work of V. Abdullayev [2], and A.Abbasbeyli and A. Hasanov dealt with issues of activity in international and regional organizations [13].

N. Mammadzade book, published in 2006, analyzes the place of Eastern European countries in the

foreign policy of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The author attaches special importance to Azerbaijan's foreign policy relations with Russia, Ukraine and Belarus. The role of national leader Heydar Aliyev in the activities of the Republic of Azerbaijan in the international arena has been reflected in many scientific works, including M. Gasimov, A. Abbasbeyli, S. Kandilov [7; 2; 4]. Azerbaijan's activity in international organizations in the years under study was an indicator of prospects, and the American political scientist Z. Brzezinski, in his scientific work on the analysis of international relations, emphasizes that Azerbaijan has the potential of a leading state in the region [14, p.146].

Since 1989, when the influence of the USSR decreased, Poland began to pursue an independent foreign policy, and before becoming a member of the North Atlantic Bloc, in 1991 Polish troops took part in the Persian Gulf War (liberation of Kuwait). Linking the success of its foreign policy in the eastern sector with democracy and independence in neighboring countries, Poland supported the independence of Ukraine and Belarus. In 1991-1992, Poland recognized the independence of Ukraine and Belarus, but the rise to power in Belarus of the Russian-inclined Alexander Lukashenko significantly strained relations with Belarus. In 1990-1991, a number of agreements were signed between the Czech and Slovak republics and Poland, in the field of trade and culture, and a visa-free regime was also introduced. The signing of the treaty between Poland and independent Lithuania lasted until April 1994 due to the problem of national minorities in both countries. Poland built bilateral relations with neighboring states on the principles of "good neighborhood, friendly cooperation", without clearly forming them. The initiator of the idea of new treaties with the countries of Eastern and Central Europe was Germany, as the latter wanted to guarantee the interests of German minorities in these states [3, p. 1-5]. The establishment of bilateral relations based on this idea was in the interests of the European Union.

The complete withdrawal of Russian troops from the territory of Poland in 1993 opened the "western gate" wide for Poland. In the early post-socialist stage, Polish foreign policy doctrine determined the need to join existing structures such as NATO and the European Union in order to maintain the stability of the country's security. At the same time, Poland could be confident in the strength of its security if Russia and its eastern neighbors were included in this system. Therefore, Warsaw has regularly advocated the establishment of close ties between NATO and Russia. Participation in the organization's operations in Bosnia and Herzegovina in 1995 is confirmed by Poland's attempts to join NATO. Preparations for joining NATO began in 1997, and in March 1999 Poland joined NATO together with the Czech and Hungarian Republics. After joining NATO, Poland became an active participant in many military operations of the North Atlantic Bloc in Europe and beyond. Poland also attracted other states -Lithuania, Latvia, Romania, Bosnia and Herzegovina - to its NATO training mission in Iraq from 2004 to 2011 [25, p.14-16].

One of the most important policy priorities of Poland, located in the middle part of Central and Eastern Europe, which emerged from the ranks of socialist countries after the collapse of the Soviet Union, was the "New Eastern Europe". Despite the high level of internal political tension and heated polemics, Polish political principles in relation to the newly independent states were accompanied by consensus, and this position was manifested in the declarations of Polish politicians. This is evidenced by the participation of Lech Walesa and Alexander Kwasniewski in the events on the Kiev Maidan in 2004. In the "National Strategy" Poland notes that democracy in Central, Eastern and Southern Europe, as well as the processes of economic transformation, the accession of these states to NATO and the European Union will affect the strengthening of peace and stability on the continent. In particular, in relations with the countries of Ukraine, Moldova, the Western Balkans, and the South Caucasus, Poland seeks to stimulate democratic development in these countries by strengthening partnerships. In this sense, the Polish leadership also considers the democratization of Belarus as a guarantee of its own security [19].

Polish diplomacy sought primarily to establish bilateral relations with its neighbors, in particular, membership in NATO and the EU required solving a number of internal issues in accordance with the standards of the Western system. In general, Poland's foreign policy in 1989-2003 was characterized by balancing Poland's actions in the international arena with the domestic situation, compliance with the political system and public opinion [9, p.7]. Poland's unexpected defense of the United States during the Iraq conflict in 2003 was a notable step in Poland's foreign policy, since such a position, which went beyond the North Atlantic, was not positively received by France and Germany. Such support on the eve of Poland's official accession to the European Union was regarded as a disloyal action against European allies. Poland's adoption of such an unexpected decision meant that in certain situations it would face the problem of choosing between the United States and the EU [11]. Some researchers consider this approach to be a product of typical geopolitical thinking for Eastern states [10, p.12]. After Poland's participation in the Iraq war, as a result of parliamentary and presidential elections, a new foreign policy course of the country was put forward. The Nationally oriented Party (PiS) sharply criticized the policy of the Republic of Poland until 2005, calling for an end. This has led to a violation of the national consensus in the field of international relations. It can be noted that the new foreign policy was developed within the framework of "historical diplomacy". The foreign policy under consideration consisted of comprehensive measures to prevent negative trends in different countries from harming Poland's interests and image. The lack of consensus has led to Poland losing its strategic aspect, becoming less transparent in the eyes of its European partners. At the dawn of the democratization process, Polish policy towards the United States was based on realism and pragmatism. Putting forward the Eastern Cooperation project on the

initiative of Poland and Sweden was a successful idea, even if the desired result was not achieved.

During these years, there has been some progress in Poland's relations with Russia. Although historically existing problems with the eastern neighbor created difficulties in building political relations, the activities of the group organized to solve complex issues could be considered an indicator of normalization of relations [8]. In 2002, the Polish-Russian group, which included government officials, historians and psychologists on complex issues, became active in 2007. From the point of view of assessing many issues, the opinions of Warsaw and Moscow differed sharply. Disagreements in geopolitical interests fueled the information war between the parties. By blocking its information resources, Poland received information about Russia from third parties, while the Kremlin constantly made humiliating broadcasts about Poles. In 2004, during the "Orange Revolution" in Ukraine, when Poland supported Yushchenko tension has increased even more. The period of Kaczynski's presidency can be seen as Poland's offensive policy in international affairs. At this time, "Eastern politics" Poland declared its main task to preserve the independence of Ukraine and Belarus, which was designed for the prospects of these countries joining NATO and the EU.

The Russian-Georgian war of 2008 and Russia's subsequent recognition of the independence of Abkhazia and Ossetia led to an aggravation of relations between the European Union and the Russian Federation. When EU members did not express a unanimous opinion on the Russian-Georgian conflict, Warsaw took an "anti-Russian" course, trying to punish Russia with isolation. [25, p.53]. The death of the Polish president and his entourage in a plane crash in Smolensk in 2010, and statements by the political opposition on this issue gave Polish-Russian relations a more negative connotation. The concepts formulated by Poland in relation to Ukraine and Belarus failed, while relations with Lithuania could not be considered positive. We can explain this situation by the lack of proper strategic planning in Poland.

Azerbaijan's membership in a number of pan-European and regional organizations, such as the OSCE, the CIS and GUAM, has played an important role in establishing mutually beneficial relations between independent Azerbaijan and various countries. Azerbaijan also maintains close contacts with the Black Sea Economic Cooperation Organization (BSEC), which has been fighting environmental crimes, terrorism, corruption and kidnapping since 1992, which includes States such as Bulgaria, Russia, Turkey and Albania. Within the framework of these structures, common political and economic interests were developed, as well as mechanisms for cooperation in the fight against international terrorism and crime.

The political relations of the Republic of Azerbaijan with neighboring Iran in 1992-1993 can be considered quite tense. During these years, official Baku made territorial claims against Iran, and serious plans were being developed in Tehran against the Azerbaijani statehood. The pro-Western policy of the Popular Front of Azerbaijan did not correspond to the

interests of Russia and Iran, and Turkey's political and economic positions in the republic were strengthening. The promotion of the slogan "greater Azerbaijan" by President Elchibey in 1992-1993 was accompanied by the strengthening of Turkish-Azerbaijani relations. In response, Iran demonstrates a tough position towards Azerbaijan, shows passivity in resolving the Karabakh conflict, and shows coldness in the issue of transit between Azerbaijan and Iran.

With the return of Heydar Aliyev to power in 1993, Azerbaijan's relations with neighboring states, including Iran, entered a qualitatively new stage. The official visit of Iranian President Ali Akbar Hashemi Rafsanjani to Azerbaijan in 1993, and a year later Heydar Aliyev to Tehran, the signing of a number of documents within the framework of the meetings gave an impetus to the rapprochement of Iranian-Azerbaijani relations, created a solid base of interstate relations. The "Contract of the century" signed in 1994 was aimed at creating an international operational consortium of Azerbaijan. 13 companies from 8 countries (Azerbaijan, USA, Japan, Great Britain, Russia, Norway, Russia, Saudi Arabia) took part in the signing of the agreement [16, p.14; 24, p.23-24]. The amount of the contract amounted to 13 billion US dollars, which attracted the attention of the world community to the Caspian region. This led to the signing of 27 more agreements involving 41 oil companies (19 countries) in the following years [22, p.107]

The Partnership and Cooperation Agreement, signed on April 22, 1996 between the European Union and Azerbaijan, provided for the development of ties in political, economic, social, cultural and a number of important areas, as well as created opportunities for the transition of relations to a better stage [1].

After the events of January 20, 1990, relations between the People's Front of Azerbaijan and Russia were extremely tense. Thanks to the authority of the Popular Front, Azerbaijan has achieved the complete withdrawal of Soviet (Russian) troops from its territory. The strengthening of Azerbaijan's relations with the West had a negative impact on its ties with Russia, which maintained a military base in Armenia. During Heydar Aliyev's visit to Moscow in 1993, the parties came to the conclusion that the low level of bilateral relations did not meet the national interests of the states. An important step towards strengthening relations was a number of documents signed during the visit.

In early 2001, the official visit of Russian President Vladimir Putin to Azerbaijan had a positive impact on bilateral relations. On February 27, 2003, the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Russian Federation signed an agreement on strengthening military-technical cooperation, and in November of the same year, a memorandum on cooperation in the space sector [17]. In a relatively short period of time, under the leadership of Heydar Aliyev, a correct strategy for the development of the state was developed by streamlining the socio-political and socio-economic situation. The leadership of the Republic of Azerbaijan has managed to establish relations with Russia, Iran, Turkey, as well as with Western countries.

Azerbaijan and Poland, which entered the period of independence, have successfully cooperated in many areas. In October 2004, during the visit of the Polish Foreign Minister to Azerbaijan, prospects for cooperation in the economic, political and military spheres were discussed. The defense cooperation project presented by Poland provided for the exchange of information, training of officers, and military-technical cooperation [15].

The GUAM Regional Organization, which includes Azerbaijan, Georgia, Ukraine and Moldova, has set a course for democracy and economic development, performs tasks such as international security, scientific and technical development. At the organization's summit in Baku in 2007, the Baku Declaration on the Creation of a Transport corridor, Strengthening Global Energy Security, and identifying ways to resolve regional conflicts fairly was adopted [20, p. 41-42].

In the 90s of the XX century and in the subsequent period, the issues of the settlement of the Azerbaijani-Armenian conflict and the return of the occupied Azerbaijani territories remained the main topics of Azerbaijan's activities in the international arena. Azerbaijan's role in the Organization of Islamic Cooperation is of particular importance in raising this issue and recognizing Armenia as an aggressor country. Speaking at the Tehran summit of the organization in 1997, the country's leader Heydar Aliyev drew the attention of the participants to Russia's support for Armenia, the supply of weapons and military equipment [6, p.127]. It was with the support of the OIC that Azerbaijani diplomacy achieved the adoption of fundamental resolutions on the occupation of Azerbaijani territories by Armenia.

Speaking at the 59th session of the UN Supreme Assembly in 2004, President Ilham Aliyev declared Armenia's non-compliance with four resolutions adopted in 1994 and proposed the creation of a working group on the implementation of resolutions. Unfortunately, the remaining UN resolutions on paper have been repeatedly voiced on the agenda of international organizations. The establishment of the Permanent Mission of the Republic of Azerbaijan to the Council of Europe in 2000 and the beginning of the activities of the Representative Office of the European Commission in the Republic of Azerbaijan, starting in 2008, are assessed as the next important steps towards strengthening ties. In January 2011, the signing of the "Joint Declaration on the Southern Gas Corridor" between President of the European Commission Jose Manuel Barroso and President of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev was carried out within the framework of the European Neighborhood Policy.

Within the framework of cooperation with NATO, the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Azerbaijan uses the Partnership for Peace, the Operational Plan for Individual Partnership, the analysis and Planning process, the Scientific Program for Peace and many other necessary mechanisms. Since 2008, the Azerbaijani Army has been cooperating with NATO within the framework of the program "Expansion of military training (DEEP)" it implements European

standards and the Bologna Process in military educational institutions.

The Republic of Azerbaijan, which adheres to the principles of joint struggle for security in the Euro-Atlantic area, participated in peacekeeping operations led by NATO. In 1999-2008, Azerbaijan was a participant in NATO operations in Kosovo (Serbia). In November 2002, a battalion of the Azerbaijani Armed Forces joined operations in Afghanistan in order to restore stability and peace.

In 2010, a number of international projects were implemented, among which the Azerbaijani-Turkish strategic cooperation and mutual assistance, Russian-Azerbaijani agreements on border issues were of great importance [21].

The collapse of the USSR allowed the Polish Republic to change its foreign policy direction and join the North Atlantic. Considering NATO as a guarantor of its security, Warsaw pays special attention to achieving maximum US assistance. One of the important aspects of Poland's activities in the international arena since its separation from the socialist system has been the acquisition by the West of the status of full members of military and integration associations. Poland, which has historically contradictory relations with Russia, acts during this period as a contender for the post of regional leader, trying to prevent neighboring countries, in particular Ukraine and Belarus, from falling under the influence of Russia. In an effort to enhance its role in Asia, the Polish Republic has used various diplomatic and economic channels for this purpose.

Over the years under study, Azerbaijan's importance in the international arena has increased, and geopolitical ties with the largest neighboring countries - Iran, Turkey and Russia - have strengthened. Western countries and the United States have begun to show increased interest in Azerbaijan and the region. In the early post-Soviet years, important steps were taken to restore relations, although many controversial issues such as the status of the Caspian Sea, the "Azerbaijani-Armenian conflict" and the transportation of energy resources created tension between Russia and Azerbaijan. Cooperation with NATO, the European Union, the OIC and many other reputable international organizations has made it possible to carry out socio-economic reforms in the republic and strengthen the state independence of Azerbaijan.

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